

In the pH range 4.75–7.50 in the case of cobalt and 4.75–7.00 in the case of nickel systems, the values of n are greater than one and less than two. So in these pH ranges, the complex C^+ dissociates to a neutral complex C and a proton according to the reaction,

It can be shown as in the cadmium citrate complex⁶ that

$$K_1 = \frac{[C][H^+]}{[C^+]} = \frac{(n-1)[H^+]}{(2-n)} \quad (4)$$

K_1 values thus calculated are 6.00×10^{-8} , 4.04×10^{-8} , 2.30×10^{-8} and 1.32×10^{-8} at pH 6.00, 6.25, 6.5 and 6.75 respectively for cobalt gluconate and 7.48×10^{-8} , 5.02×10^{-8} , 3.39×10^{-8} and 2.17×10^{-8} at pH 6.25, 6.5, 6.75 and 7.00 respectively for nickel gluconate complex.

Cobalt and nickel gluconates are precipitated above pH 7.5 and 7.0 respectively. The cobalt and nickel contents of these precipitates, estimated by pyridine thiocyanate method, are found to be 23.13% and 23.07% respectively, which corresponds to the formation of 1 : 1 metal gluconate complex.

Fig. 3 : pH titration of 50.0 ml. of solution containing 6.25×10^{-4} g. mole of sodium gluconate and 5.0×10^{-8} g. mole sodium perchlorate (Curve A) and that of the same volume of another solution containing same quantity of the above constituents and 5.0×10^{-4} g. mole of cobalt perchlorate (Curve B) against 0.1M sodium hydroxide.

Fig. 4 : pH titration of 50.0 ml. of solution containing 6.25×10^{-4} g. mole of sodium gluconate and 5.0×10^{-8} g. mole of sodium perchlorate (Curve A) and that of the same volume of another solution containing same quantity of the above constituents and 5.0×10^{-4} g. mole nickel sulphate (Curve B) against 0.1M sodium hydroxide.

The complexes C^+ and C are present in the pH ranges 4.5–7.5 and 4.5–7.0 for cobalt and nickel systems respectively in experiments 3 and 4.

It can be shown as in the manganese tartrate⁸ complex that

$$[C] = [H^+] + [NaOH] + \frac{[TGI]_B - [Metal\ salt]}{b} \quad (5)$$

K_1 values calculated as before are found to be 1.19×10^{-8} , 1.29×10^{-8} and 1.41×10^{-8} at pH 7.1, 7.2 and 7.3 respectively for cobalt and 1.1×10^{-8} , 1.25×10^{-8} and 1.5×10^{-8} at pH 6.90, 6.95 and 7.00 respectively for nickel system. The mean values of K_1 are 1.29×10^{-8} and 1.28×10^{-8} for cobalt and nickel systems respectively which are in good agreement with the results obtained in the experiments 1 and 2.

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Complex Compounds of Bi- and Tri-Valent Silver

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THOUGH Silver (II) exhibits a strong oxidising property, still the higher oxidation state of silver has been stabilised by co-ordination with many nitrogen containing heterocyclic bases¹. The oxidation potential of Ag (I) to Ag (II) is rather high, being 1.914 volts in nitric acid solution and 1.41 volts in alkaline solution, but these values are considerably lowered by co-ordination. Further all the complexes are very insoluble in aqueous medium; as such even in presence of these strongly oxidising agents, number of these complexes have been synthesised fairly easily.

In the present communication, the preparation and properties of a few complexes of Ag(II) with *p*-phenetylbisguanide and Ag(III) with 2-guanidinobenzimidazole molecule have been described.

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Experimental**A : Silver(II) Complexes :**

α -Silver(II)-*p*-phenethylbiguanidinium sulphate : Silver sulphate, *p*-phenethylbiguanide sulphate and potassium peroxodisulphate were taken in a large beaker and then water was added with constant stirring. A red solution was gradually obtained and finally the colour deepened to dark red. The solution was quickly filtered. From the filtrate dirty yellow microscopic crystals separated. These were filtered, washed with ice cold water and dried in air. The dried substance was brownish yellow in colour and was stable at room temperature. It dissolved in dilute HCl giving a dark red solution.

Silver(III) - 2-guanidinobenzimidazole sulphate : 2-Guanidinobenzimidazole was dissolved in minimum quantity of dilute sulphuric acid (2*N*). To this were added solutions of silver sulphate and potassium peroxodisulphate. The red solution slowly deepened in colour and it was quickly filtered. From the filtrate, on keeping overnight in the cold, very fine brownish red crystals separated out. These were filtered, washed with cold water and dried in air. The substance was quite stable at room temperature and dissolved in dilute HCl giving a dark red solution.

(Found : C, 28.6 ; H, 5.4 ; N, 20.9 ; SO₄, 14.9 ; H₂O, 21.0 ; Ag, 10.6 ; Ag (oxidimetric), 10.7 per cent.)

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTIC DATA OF SILVER(II) COMPLEXES.

Compounds	Colour	Magnetic Moment (in B.M.)	Found (%)					Calculated (%)					Absorption (cm ⁻¹)
			C	H	N	Ag	SO ₄	C	H	N	Ag	SO ₄	
α -[Ag(L) ₂]SO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	Yellow brown	1.90	35.0	5.1	20.3	15.8 (15.9)	14.1	35.2	5.0	20.5	15.8	14.8	24,800 br
β -[Ag(L) ₂]SO ₄ ·H ₂ O	Black	1.85			21.1	16.3 (16.2)	14.5			21.1	16.3	14.5	25,500 br
α -[Ag(L) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ ·H ₂ O	Black	1.85			23.9	15.5 (15.4)				24.2	15.6		25,450 br
β -[Ag(L) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ ·H ₂ O	Black	1.87			23.8	15.5 (15.3)				24.2	15.6		25,200 br

L = *p*-Phenethylbiguanide (C₁₀H₁₅N₅O)

Figures in parenthesis is silver by oxidimetric method.

β -Silver(II)-*p*-phenethylbiguanidinium sulphate : Potassium peroxodisulphate solution was added to a cold solution of silver sulphate. The solution immediately became dark and to this was added excess of *p*-phenethylbiguanide sulphate with stirring. It was kept in the cold for two hours when the colour changed to deep red, appearing almost black. From the solution a black microcrystalline substance separated. It was filtered, washed thoroughly with cold water and dried in air. The α -variety was soluble in cold conc. HCl.

α -Silver(II)-*p*-phenethylbiguanidinium nitrate : This was prepared from the α -sulphate by dissolving the sulphate in freshly prepared cold dilute NaOH solution. The slightly alkaline solution was then quickly neutralised with dilute nitric acid. From the solution brown microscopic crystals separated. These were filtered, washed with cold water and while drying changed to black in colour.

β -Silver(II)-*p*-phenethylbiguanidinium nitrate : When the β -sulphate was treated with cold and dilute NaOH, a brown solution was obtained. This was carefully neutralised with nitric acid and on cooling, black crystals of the nitrate separated. These were filtered, washed and dried in the usual way. The substance was equally stable as the sulphate.

B : Silver(III) Complexes :

Calc. for [Ag(C₈H₉N₅)₃] 1.5SO₄·12H₂O : C, 29.0 ; H, 5.1 ; N, 21.1 ; SO₄, 14.5 ; H₂O, 21.7 ; Ag, 10.9 per cent.)

Results and Discussion

Silver(II) : By peroxodisulphate oxidation of Silver(I), in presence of the ligand *p*-phenethylbiguanidinium sulphate (pH : 5-6.5), two varieties (yellowish brown and black) of silver(II) complexes were formed. The corresponding nitrates formed only one type, and that was black in colour. The complexes separated with one or two mols of water of hydration, and complete loss of water was observed below 100°. The magnetic susceptibility was measured in a Curie balance and the complexes were all paramagnetic with magnetic moments between 1.85—1.90 B. M. Their acid solutions liberated one electron equivalent iodine from potassium iodide solution. As reported, moments significantly in excess of 2.0 B. M., are not expected for octahedral or square planar silver(II) complexes³, whereas for a tetrahedral arrangement, magnetic moment should be in excess of 2.0 B. M. These complexes in their diffused reflectance spectra, show an absorption band near 25,000 cm⁻¹, which correspond to the d-d transition associated bands of the square planar silver(II) complexes^{3,4}. Conductivity and spectral properties in solution could not be performed due to the insolubility of these compounds in non-polar solvents.

Silver(III): The state of oxidation of silver(III) can also be stabilised by co-ordination with some nitrogen containing organic bases⁵, and three inorganic anions: fluoride, per-iodate and tellurate. Curiously enough, all these complexes separate out with several molecules of hydration water, usually 7-18 H₂O. The oxidation with K₂S₂O₈ of a cold aq. solution of a mixture of biguanide sulphate and AgNO₃ at pH 6.5-7.0 has in fact been claimed to yield sparingly soluble brown crystals of Ag(C₂H₇N₅)(OH)(SO₄)·7H₂O⁶. All these compounds are diamagnetic.

Thermogravimetric analyses of the silver complex revealed that there was gradual loss of water molecules starting from a temperature of 60° with complete loss of water at 140°; further rise in temperature resulted in thermal decomposition of the anhydrous complex.

The compound was diamagnetic and oxidised two equivalents of iodide per gram-atom of silver. In this complex silver showed a co-ordination number six, which is rather uncommon for this group of ter-valent ions.

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Thermal Decomposition Studies on Chromium(III) Complexes with Hydroxamic Acids

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SEVERAL workers have studied transition metal complexes thermogravimetrically including chromium(III)¹ to establish their thermal properties. This communication deals with the thermal decomposition studies of few tris(hydroxamato) chromium(III) complexes.

Results and Discussion

The thermal decomposition curve of tris(salicylhydroxamato)-chromium(III) indicated that the complex was stable upto 70° and after that it suffered decomposition. Two breaks were observed at 220° and 360° respectively. The break observed at 220° corresponded to the loss of two-third ligand molecule.

(Found: 0.2190 g.; calcd: 0.22006 g.). The decomposition of the latter compound began at 360° giving a residue of Cr₂O₃ beginning at 500° (Fig I, curve b). The decomposition may be represented as:

Fig. 1

The thermograms for tris(phenylacetylhydroxamato) chromium(III) (Fig I, Curve a) showed that the complex suffered no loss upto 80° and after that a break was observed at 220° which corresponded to the two-third loss of the ligand (Found; 0.2350 g., calcd.: 0.2302 g.). However, no break was observed for the loss of the remaining ligand molecule as found in case of tris(salicylhydroxamato) chromium(III). The residual product of the pyrolysis was Cr₂O₃ beginning at 460°.

The weight-loss curve of tris(benzohydroxamato) chromium(III) (Fig. I, Curve c) indicated that there was no appreciable loss of the compound upto 70° and after that it suffered decomposition. Although two breaks were noted in the curve at 300° and 420° respectively, no definite stoichiometry could be assigned to these. The terminal product, however, was Cr₂O₃.

No attempt has been made to formulate the intermediates in any case.

Experimental

The syntheses, characterisation spectral data, i.r. and magnetic properties have been described earlier². The thermograms were recorded in air on a Stanton thermobalance (high temperature model, 1mg. sensitivity) from 0° to 600°. Heating rate was 10° per minute.